

ISR enters its 8th year with a new publication

AISDL Team

August 1, 2024

[Science Communication]

Today marks the 7th anniversary of the Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research (ISR), at Phenikaa University. ISR has for seven years now the place where the co-founders of this portal have been working and producing publications.

A special event occurs now as the Current Conservation magazine publishes a new writing piece by our member, Dr Minh-Hoang Nguyen [1].

Illustration: Screenshot of the article by Dr Nguyen [1].

This article also mentions several books published by the founder of ISR, i.e. [2-3].

It is such a pleasure reading a decent article on a special day like this. Congratulations to Dr Minh-Hoang Nguyen on this not-a-small feat.

And, last but not least, Happy Birthday to ISR.

References

- [1] Nguyen MH. (2024). A life-long humanistic journey to conservation practices. *Current Conservation*, **18**(3). <https://www.currentconservation.org/a-life-long-humanistic-journey-to-conservation-practices/>
- [2] Vuong QH. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>
- [3] Vuong QH. (2023). *Meandering Sobriety*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOC2TXNX6L>
- [4] Vuong QH. (Ed.) (2022). *A New Theory of Serendipity: Nature, Emergence and Mechanism*. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter.

